

Impact of Training Programmes in Digital Skills to Reduce Unwanted Loneliness in Older Andalusian Women

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Abstract. This study evaluates the impact of training sessions and follow-up workshops focused on digital skills among older Andalusian women, with the ultimate goal of reducing unwanted loneliness through handheld technology, specifically social networks and tablets. The research presents a comparative analysis of social groups with various educational sessions aimed at older women, highlighting the significant role of human interaction and strategic planning in these workshops. The findings underscore the need for customised educational interventions that promote adherence and effective use of technology among this demographic. The study shows the critical need for well-structured training sessions that address both technical skills and the social dimensions of technology use among older adults.

Keywords: training sessions · digital skills · unwanted loneliness · active ageing

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1 Introduction

The demographic transition towards an increasingly aged population is a global phenomenon that is reshaping social and economic structures worldwide. This shift is attributed to a combination of factors such as declining fertility rates and increased life expectancy, resulting in a significant increase in both the number and the proportion of older people. This demographic surge presents unique challenges and opportunities, particularly in terms of the adoption of new technologies to improve the quality of life of older adults. The importance of adopting and adapting new technologies for the ageing population lies in addressing the challenges associated with ageing, including healthcare, emotional

well-being, promotion of autonomy, and prevention of dependency [6]. Emerging technologies such as telemedicine, home health monitoring devices, and personal or cognitive wellness applications are crucial to improve healthcare and enabling greater independence for seniors. Likewise, digital communication technologies such as social networks can have a profound impact on the social sphere, reducing loneliness and fostering meaningful social connections [1, 7].

However, despite the transformative potential of these technologies, significant barriers hamper their widespread adoption among older adults [8]. One key barrier is the lack of digital skills and low technological literacy within this demographic group. Many seniors have not had the same exposure or access to technology as younger generations, leading to a significant digital divide. Unfamiliarity with devices such as computers, tablets, or smartphones can be an initial hurdle to embracing new technologies. Another significant barrier is the negative perception or fear of technology among some older individuals. For many, the idea of learning to use new technological tools can be overwhelming or intimidating, stemming from past negative experiences or a general aversion to the unfamiliar. Furthermore, digital interfaces designed without considering the specific needs of older adults, such as vision impairments or reduced motor skills, can pose a significant challenge to adoption [5].

Addressing these barriers requires specific, customised approaches to facilitate digital inclusion among seniors. Education and training in technological literacy designed specifically for this demographic are essential. Training programmes can help develop basic skills in using technological devices and build confidence in their handling. It is crucial to design programmes tailored to this population, as programme type often determines learning outcomes and ultimately device usage. Including also awareness of the importance of such technologies in quality of life or in improving other health and social variables in the lives of older people [2]. In addition to addressing individual barriers, systemic challenges that affect the adoption of technology by older adults must also be considered. These include issues of physical and economic access to technology, as well as the availability of technical support services and customer care tailored to this age group. Public policies can also play a crucial role in promoting digital inclusion through technological literacy initiatives and device acquisition subsidy programmes [8]. In summary, the ageing population and the increasing number of older adults underscore the critical importance of harnessing new technologies to improve the quality of life and care of this demographic group. However, to maximise the positive impact of these innovations, it is essential to address existing barriers to technology adoption by older adults, from technological literacy to inclusive design and equitable access to digital infrastructure.

1.1 Aim and Hypothesis

In this context, the objective of this article is to determine the importance of training and follow-up programmes for this population of older adults in their

future acquisition and use of technology. Hence, our initial hypothesis is that continuous and individualised training and follow-up will lead to better outcomes in technology usage and dropout index among the adult population compared to a limited and unsupported training and follow-up programme.

2 Materials and Methods

In this section, we present the methods, inclusion criteria, and evaluation groups used in the study. This detailed description ensures a clear understanding of the procedures and the specific characteristics required for participants' eligibility. The section also outlines the distinct groups formed for assessment purposes, each designed to measure different outcomes based on the defined criteria.

2.1 Research context

This specific study is part of a broader protocol within the Andalusian pilot of the large-scale Pharaon project (Pilots for Healthy and Active Ageing). Specifically, this study implemented a series of interoperable technological devices that are part of the Pharaon catalogue. These devices are adapted to the needs of older adults in the Andalusian pilot [4], and therefore three technological scenarios were set up; 1) socialisation scenario (Sentab social network), 2) activity monitoring scenario (Miss Activity pocket sensor), 3) Cognitive Stimulation Scenario (NeuronUP, cognitive stimulation platform). This study focusses only on the socialisation scenario.

The general aim of the Pharaon project is to test technology in older adults [5] and to understand its impact on their health (measured using different metrics). However, this study does not focus on the impact of technology on health, but rather on the importance of designing training and follow-up programmes that affect the use of such technology. Therefore, we tested how 3 different training and follow-up protocols (2 with on-demand follow-up and one without follow-up) affect subsequent usage.

2.2 Inclusion criteria

Older women 65 years or older living in Andalusia. They are alone or feel lonely. They do not present cognitive impairment that prevents them from making decisions autonomously and independently. The total sample included: 122 Older women from several villages of Andalusia (Martos, La Carolina, La Puerta de Segura, Arjona, Bailén, Alcaudete, Fuerte del Rey, Castillo de Locubín, Huelma, Santiesteban del Puerto, Mengíbar, Rus, Los Villares, Torredelcampo, Torres, Jaén, Baeza, Villacarrillo, Canena and Porcuna).

2.3 Exclusion criteria

Exclusion criteria for the study include individuals who have withdrawn from the programme (16) and those for whom sociodemographic data could not be obtained for analysis (6). These exclusions ensure that the study results reflect accurate and complete information from participants fully engaged in the intervention and for whom comprehensive background data are available.

2.4 Questionnaires and data collection

In the study, a variety of questionnaires were used to collect quantitative data to investigate the impact of continuous training compared to single session training on the use of the Sentab social network application among older adults. The tools were designed to collect sociodemographic information from the sample, as well as specific data on the participant's experience and use of the app.

- Sociodemographic questionnaires include multiple variables: age, gender, educational level, degree of dependency, and level of technological experience. Specifically, we specify some variables:
 - Education ISCED, Based on International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED), reference for organizing educational programmes and related qualifications by levels and fields. ISCED levels: early childhood education, primary education, lower secondary education, upper secondary education, post-secondary non-tertiary education, short-cycle tertiary education, bachelor's or equivalent level, master's or equivalent level, doctoral or equivalent level.
 - Demographic 6. Degree of dependency assessed according to the Spanish Law 39/2006, of December 14, on the Promotion of Personal Autonomy and Care for People in a Situation of Dependence (Spanish Law) where the dependency is based on 3 levels: grade 1 (moderate dependency), grade 2 (severe dependency), grade 3 (high dependency), (4) Demographic 13. Living status. Alone / not alone, (5) Demographic 14. Technology experience. Yes / No.
- Data Collection on App Use Frequency: The frequency of use of the Sentab app was measured through given technological indicators provided by the OneSait platform, which collects quantitative data that are reported in real-time to the platform. In this work, the next dimensions are computed in order to evaluate 3 dimensions of use:
 - Low/None use. In the case of number of user interactions with the Sentab platform is less than 100 (within the year of evaluation).

- Medium use. In the case of the number of user interactions with the Sentab platform is higher than or equal to 100 and lower than 365 (within the year of evaluation).
- High use. In the case where the number of user interactions with the Sentab platform is greater than 365, this is a one-day interaction as average (within the year of evaluation).

2.5 Procedures and evaluation groups

After the deployment of the technology, initial individual and group training sessions were held. Individual sessions were held in nursing homes and lasted between one and half / two hours. The group sessions were held in the Social Services Centres of the municipalities and in the Residential Centres for older adults, lasting between two and three hours. Between 9 and 15 participants have participated in these sessions. Basic concepts of digital literacy were taught in the training sessions. Training on the use of the tablet technological device began: how to turn on the tablet, how to charge the tablet, basic tablet controls, how to navigate the Internet. Then, once they learnt how to use the device, they were explained how to use the Sentab social networking app, which they have used for 12 months.

Once the initial training sessions were completed, participants were randomly assigned to three different groups: Group 1 (G1) with ongoing training prioritising individual sessions, Group 2 (G2) with ongoing training prioritising group sessions, and Group 3 (G3) with a single session training. A random assignment method was used to minimise bias and ensure comparability between groups. All groups had access to the Sentab application for a period of 12 months.

- Group 1 and 2 (G1, G2). Continuing training. Group of participants who received ongoing training on the Sentab social networking application. This additional training was designed to strengthen and update the knowledge acquired during the initial training sessions. The continuing training sessions were conducted in person and addressed new developments of the platform, as well as practical advice to maximise the experience of the participants. In addition to face-to-face sessions, continuous monitoring was initiated through telephone calls, email (created exclusively for the study) and via WhatsApp. These weekly and biweekly communications allowed feedback to be established with the participants, providing the opportunity to resolve doubts, provide technical assistance, and collect comments about their experience with the application. In addition, 5 monthly one hour group video calls were held. During these video calls, participants had the opportunity to share their experience with the application, interact with each other, and share experiences from their life history, tastes, preferences, and any other topic of common interest. These video calls strengthened the bond between participants and provided a space for knowledge sharing and community building

around the use of the Sentab app. To encourage the use of the application and increase motivation, voluntary activities were proposed through the application itself. These activities were designed to involve users in app usage practices, such as posting content, interacting with other users, participating in discussion groups, or sharing relevant events and news. These voluntary activities not only served to consolidate the learning and practice of the knowledge acquired in the training sessions, but also contributed to creating an active and participatory community around the use of Sentab.

- G1. The training sessions were developed individually face to face between the stakeholder and the elderly woman.
 - G2. Training sessions were developed in social groups face-to-face between stakeholders and elderly women.
- Group 3 (G3): Single training. Participants who received a single training session on the same topic as Group 1 (G1) focused on basic use of the Sentab social networking application. During this initial session, instructions on how to turn on and use the tablet were provided, as well as an introduction to the basic operation of the Sentab application, including how to navigate the platform and use its main functions.

Unlike G1-G2, G3 participants did not receive additional training or follow-up on the use and functionalities of the Sentab application. The follow-up they received focused exclusively on technical issues and technological incidents, such as internet connection problems, technical difficulties with the tablet, or any other difficulty related to the device or application. Therefore, this group provides an important comparison point to evaluate the impact of ongoing training and regular follow-up offered to G1-G2 compared to one-time training without ongoing follow-up in G3.

3 Results

This section presents the results of the sociodemographic characteristics and the use of technology among the different groups within the study.

3.1 Homogeneous sociodemographic data across the groups

In order to demonstrate the homogeneity of the social groups G1, G2 and G3, we have analysed the sociodemographic variables by computing the mean and standard deviation and providing the p values of the t test for the correlations (see Table 1, Table 2 and Figure 1).

As we observe, there is no significant differentiation between the populations of groups G1, G2, and G3. The only notable distinction is in age between groups G1 and G3, with G3 being slightly younger.

Table 1. Sociodemographic variables (mean and standard deviation across groups).

Variable (obtained from questionnaires)	G1 (μ, σ)	G2 (μ, σ)	G3 (μ, σ)
Year of birth	(1944.32, 8.28)	(1946.03, 9.95)	(1948.39, 7.00)
ISCED	(1.26, 1.46)	(1.03, 1.15)	(0.82, 1.39)
DIM 6	(0.23, 0.55)	(0.16, 0.51)	(0.25, 0.57)
DIM 13	(0.23, 0.42)	(0.19, 0.40)	(0.14, 0.35)
DIM 14	(0.16, 0.37)	(0.29, 0.45)	(0.21, 0.62)

Table 2. Correlation of sociodemographic variables by t-test and p-values across groups.

Variable (obtained from questionnaires)	G1-G2	G2-G3	G1-G3
Year of birth	t: -0.8661 p: 0.3899	t: -1.2761 p: 0.2071	t: -1.9925 p: 0.0511
ISCED	t: 0.6660 p: 0.5080	t: 0.6261 p: 0.5337	t: 1.1540 p: 0.2533
DIM 6	t: 0.4688 p: 0.6409	t: -0.6151 p: 0.5410	t: -0.1621 p: 0.8718
DIM 13	t: 0.3071 p: 0.7598	t: 0.5105 p: 0.6117	t: 0.8075 p: 0.4227
DIM 14	t: -1.2097 p: 0.2311	t: 0.5325 p: 0.5965	t: -0.3975 p: 0.6925

3.2 Homogeneous sociodemographic data across the groups

In this section, we analyse the impact of training programmes on the use of technology by older Andalusian women. To this end, we have categorised the quantitative variable 'number of interactions' with the Sentab platform based on three terms (low, medium and high) to determine whether a user has had little to no use, moderate or high use, respectively (see Section 2.2, Table 3, Table 4 and Figure 2).

Table 3. Classification of users based on the use of technology (mean and standard deviation across groups).

Use of technology (number of interactions)	G1 (μ, σ)	G2 (μ, σ)	G3 (μ, σ)
low/none	(0.58, 0.49)	(0.52, 0.50)	(0.93, 0.26)
medium	(0.19, 0.40)	(0.26, 0.42)	(0.04, 0.18)
high	(0.26, 0.44)	(0.23, 0.41)	(0.04, 0.18)

As we can see, the use of technology has been successful in groups G1 and G2, in terms of medium and high use due to continuous training and workshops, although they kept a significant low use (close to 50%). The lack of monitoring in workshops of the G3 group has generated a generalised low use of 93%,

Table 4. Correlation of use of technology by t-test and p-values across groups.

Use of technology (number of interactions)	G1-G2	G2-G3	G1-G3
low/none	t: 0.5032 p: 0.6167	t: -3.8550 p: 0.0003	t: -3.2852 p: 0.0017
medium		t: 2.4513	t: 1.8973
	p: 0.5512	p: 0.0173	p: 0.0629
high	t: 0.2919	t: 2.1787	t: 2.4513
	p: 0.7713	p: 0.0335	p: 0.0173

highlighting the great impact and difference in use carried out by continuous follow-up.

4 Conclusions

As previously stated, this research aimed to highlight the importance of ongoing training and support for older adults in learning and continuing to use technology, and to evaluate how such support influences usage frequency and other factors. The findings underscore the essential role of sustained, tailored training and support initiatives for the older adult population. These initiatives not only improve technological competence, but also play a crucial role in enabling this group to adopt and effectively use technology.

Participants who participated in regular training and support showed higher rates of technology use, which translated into better use of technology in everyday life. Furthermore, our data indicate that whether sessions are conducted individually (G1) or in groups (G2), the frequency of use of technology remains unaffected. Hence, the effectiveness of promoting the use of technology lies in the consistency of the support provided. The review of the literature [3] pinpoints at least five obstacles or challenges that hinder the acquisition of digital skills among older adults: 1) age-related issues, 2) technology design or feature-related problems, 3) perceived self-efficacy deficits, 4) adverse societal perceptions, and 5) the complexity of educational materials. Furthermore, our research suggests that the nature of the training programme significantly influences learning outcomes and subsequent use of technology. In this context, it has been demonstrated that well-structured post-training support programmes are effective in technology adoption, potentially influencing technology dropout rates among adults. It is believed that ongoing support and addressing individual concerns are crucial in keeping older adults engaged and active in the use of technology, thus improving their retention and maximising the advantages of technology.

These insights, although clear, carry significant importance and can inform future guidelines. They underscore the necessity for public policies that foster training and follow-up initiatives designed specifically for older adults. By focusing on tailored technological education for this group, substantial enhancements

in their life quality, independence, and overall well-being can be achieved. Consequently, it is vital to develop robust strategies that enable older adults to reap the full benefits of technological advancements, thus improving their well-being and quality of life in today's digital era by ensuring easy access to new technologies, providing educational programs, and offering consistent support.

This research also illustrates the transformative impact of technology on social integration and communication among older adults. It underscores the need to design interfaces and software that specifically cater to the ergonomic and cognitive needs of the older demographic, facilitating a more inclusive digital environment. This approach not only empowers older adults, but also integrates them more fully into the digital world, thus bridging the generational digital divide. Moving forward, our recommendations call for more proactive participation from technology designers and policy makers to consider the unique needs of the ageing population in technology development and deployment. This will ensure that technological advances are accessible and beneficial to all age groups, thus fostering a more inclusive society.

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Fig. 1. Sociodemographic variables (mean and standard deviation across groups).

Fig. 2. Classification of users based on the use of technology (mean and standard deviation across groups).